

THE ROLE OF BOOK CULTURE IN YOUTH EDUCATION.

Annotation: this article describes the importance of the book in the education of young people, the culture of reading.

Keywords: book, spirituality, duty, knowledge, culture, Family, School .

The book is an important source that raises the spirituality and worldview of man . A person who reads a book is thoughtful, educated, distinguished from others by his worldview and thinking with a high level of thinking . A child with a book grows up as a good person . Therefore, it is the duty of parents, teachers to increase children's affection for the book, interest in literature, both in the family, in kindergartens and in schools .

The book is a source of knowledge . He can protect a person from all sorts of shameful deeds, from evil intentions . Therefore, the book is considered to be the best friend, companion and confidant of man . The book does not have the language of his friend . From the conversation of the book, a person will only benefit . Such a delightful benefit can not be found from anything else, from anyone . The person who reads the book is aware of the past and looks at the future with a thoughtful glance .

About the book it is possible to talk about every number,praising its qualities for hours. The reason is that the best friend, the confidant, the most necessary companion is a book, the greatest and most valuable of all inventions discovered in the history of mankind, a miracle that,if the times have passed, has not emptied its place to anyone.

When great scientists express their opinion about the book, reading, they say that with literature, a fellow soul will never build a nest of evil . The role and importance of the book in the awareness of national self, the formation of high spirituality in our youth, the upbringing of them as owners of noble qualities are inseparable.

The level of knowledge of a person who reads many books is high, the culture of treatment is high, he can find his place in life as a mature person . However, today the need and aspiration for a book, reading a book, is increasingly declining, especially among young people . And this is very painful. Near books, book shelves and bookshelves simply stand as a spectacle . The natural question arises. Why is it so? Why are we reading books?

A thousand, unfortunately, are not few among us people who spend their valuable time on idyllic entertainment instead of reading books . They show that they are not high in spirituality, even in thinking, in self-esteem . We live in the era of the technical Age, Day by day the technical means are developing and the need for them is increasing. In particular, hand phones, we can make different internet systems as example of this. In our country, young people are provided with wide opportunities. Because it is these young people who raise the dignity of our nation, our national pride. Therefore, we should arouse affection to the book in the minds of our youth. It is also of educational importance to accustom the students to work with the book. Reading increases the spiritual wealth of young people, makes them work

and start a creative path. The book helps to realize the glory of life, to think about it independently.

In place of the conclusion, it should be said that the importance of the book in the current globalization conditions

further increase, development of reading culture is an urgent requirement of today. Because the book retains its original Psycho - aesthetic charm, the power of influence, and after that it remains the same.

List of used literature:

1. M. Miroshyeva " educational technologies and pedagogical skills . T-2015
2. www.siyona.net
3. New Librarian Strategy 2022 y
4. Kattil Usanovich (Bauer), & Nihalie Ise Rayrena Nazareta (2022). education in the formation of youth life strategy. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (TEXTU Conference 1), 830-833

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